

Identification of Households Prone to Income Underreporting: Employment Status or Reported Business Income?

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Abstract:

Pissarides and Weber (1989) propose using data on income and food consumption for estimating the extent of income underreporting by the self-employed, a group seen to be prone to income underreporting. This paper is the first to investigate the importance of the way in which these households are identified in such analyses. Using household budget data from Estonia, different ways are used to identify households prone to income underreporting and to estimate the extent of the underreporting. The share of unreported income is estimated to be substantially larger when underreporting households are identified using their share of reported business income than when they are identified using their employment status. Further analysis combines the different identification methods and reveals that the employment status provides no information on underreporting when the share of business income is taken into account. The share of reported business income is the most informative indicator of underreporting.

Keywords: income underreporting, business income, self-employment, Engel curve

JEL codes: H26, E21, E26, H24

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1. Introduction

Pissarides and Weber (1989) proposed a new methodology for estimating the extent of income underreporting by the self-employed, a group of taxpayers that are usually seen as prone to underreporting their income. The idea is to compare the relation between reported consumption and income for the self-employed and for people that are not self-employed. This paper is the first to examine the importance of the way the self-employed, i.e. the households prone to underreporting, are identified in empirical studies using the methodology of Pissarides and Weber (1989).

It is typically easier for the self-employed to underreport their income to tax and statistics authorities than it is for wage earners. Information on the income of employed individuals is available to the authorities through third-party reporting, while the self-employed typically have substantial discretion over the income reported as audits of income and deductions are infrequent or imprecise (Soos 1990). These differences suggest that the self-employed may underreport income to a larger extent than households of wage earners. Bruce (2000) posits that the chance to underreport represents an incentive for people to choose to be self-employed. The experimental study of Alm, Deskins and McKee (2009) shows that individuals with a higher share of income not reported to the tax authority by a third party exhibit lower tax compliance.

It is challenging to estimate the extent of underreporting by the self-employed. Pissarides and Weber (1989) or P&W estimate the extent of underreporting by using information on food consumption and income from the UK household budget survey. The underlying idea is that households are likely to report their consumption expenses relatively precisely as the households produce detailed consumption accounts for the survey, while some households may underreport

their income to the statistics office. The extent of income underreporting by the self-employed is then estimated from an Engel food consumption function that includes a shift term for self-employed households. The main identifying assumption is that self-employed households and other types of households, *ceteris paribus*, have the same propensity to consume out of their total (reported and unreported) income.

Underreporting of income to a statistics office does not necessarily entail underreporting to the tax authority. Pissarides and Weber (1989) argue, however, that households may seek not to report higher income to a household budget survey than they do to the tax authority as the survey respondents may fear that information is exchanged between the statistics office and the tax authority. Paulus (2015a) finds, using data for 2007 and 2008, a substantial overlap between the reporting of households to the Estonian Social Survey and to the Estonian tax authorities. The results may thus be seen as an indication of possible tax evasion by the self-employed.

Pissarides and Weber (1989) use data from the 1982 Family Expenditure Survey for the UK and find that the share of total (reported and unreported) income not reported by the self-employed is 23-39 percent. The estimated income underreporting is *relative to the comparison group*, meaning that the estimate depicts the underreporting of self-employed households *on top of* the possible underreporting by the comparison group. In many cases, however, households that only have income from employment would not easily be able to underreport their income because of third-party reporting (Pissarides and Weber 1989).

After a hiatus, a number of studies have been published using the P&W methodology for different countries. Schuetze (2002) uses Canadian data for six years within the time period 1969-1992 and finds that self-employed households left 11-23 percent of income unreported relative to

the comparison group of wage earners. Johansson (2005) uses data from the 1994-1996 Finnish household budget surveys and estimates that the share of unreported income is 10-24 percent if one person in the household is self-employed and 37-47 percent if two people are self-employed. Hurst, Li and Pugsley (2014) use data from two different surveys from the USA covering around 20 years and reach very similar results from both data sources, finding that households that state their employment status as self-employed underreport around 30 percent of their income.

Gibson, Kim and Chung (2009) are the first to use data from countries outside Western Europe and North America. They estimate the underreporting share of the self-employed in South Korea to be around 38 percent (data for 2000-2005), while the underreporting share in Russia amounts to 47 percent (data for 1994-2000). Kukk and Staehr (2014) use data from Estonia for 2002-2007 and find that the underreporting share of the self-employed in Estonia is around 62 percent of their total reported and unreported income.

Two other papers are of particular relevance for this paper. Engström and Holmlund (2009) consider underreporting in Sweden using data for 1999-2004. They find an underreporting share of 15-20 percent for self-employed households with an incorporated business and 40-50 percent for households with an unincorporated business. Paulus (2015b) uses data from the Estonian Social Survey and Estonian tax records for 2007 and 2008 and finds an underreporting share by the self-employed of 56 percent when the comparison group consists of *wage earners in the public sector*. These papers suggest that different classifications of the self-employed and the comparison group may be important for the results.

The P&W methodology prescribes the division of the sample into two groups: those deemed prone to underreporting income and the comparison group deemed less likely to

underreport income. Two different methods for dividing the sample are used in the literature. One method considers the *share of reported business income* in reported income and defines a household as prone to underreporting if the share exceeds a given threshold. The other method uses the *employment status* reported by the household and defines a household as prone to underreporting if self-employment is the reported employment status. The first method, based on the share of reported business income, is used in Pissarides and Weber (1989), Schuetze (2002) and Kukk and Staehr (2014). The second method, based on the reported employment status, is used in Hurst, Li and Pugsley (2014), Johansson (2005), Engström and Holmlund (2009) and Paulus (2015b).

Pissarides and Weber (1989) is the only paper to discuss the identification choice. They state that they reach similar results when using either of the two methods to identify households prone to underreporting, but they only provide the results when the households are identified using the reported share of business income. All other studies use one of the identification methods and do not investigate whether the particular choice is important for the results, probably because of data availability. Although household budget surveys may contain data on both reported employment status and business income, income data are typically not collected at a detailed level and data on business income may therefore not be available.¹ Moreover, in some household budget surveys the time periods of the consumption and income data do not match.²

This paper is the first to present a detailed analysis of the consequences of the choice of method for identifying the households that may be prone to income underreporting. The Estonian Household Budget Survey (HBS) for the period 2002-2007 is uniquely suited for this analysis because the survey contains questions that make it possible to use both identification methods.

The survey collects detailed information both on consumption and on different income sources and there is no mismatch between the periods of consumption and income data.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 provides a discussion of the Estonian economy, the tax system and ways of underreporting income. Section 3 presents the dataset used and provides summary statistics on the two different identification methods. Section 4 introduces the empirical model. Section 5 presents the main underreporting results when the two identification methods are used separately. Section 6 considers the combination of different identification methods. Finally, Section 7 concludes.

2. The tax system and tax compliance in Estonia

Estonia regained its independence from the Soviet Union in 1991. It embarked on an ambitious reform process and by the end of the 1990s it exhibited a market economy with a small public sector and a low tax intake relative to GDP (Staehr 2004). Fiscal policy is prudent and in rankings of fiscal management Estonia is typically placed alongside or above most Western European countries (Fabrizio and Mody 2010). The policy of e-governance has let individuals and firms file their taxes online since 2000.

The Estonian tax system is simple (Staehr 2009). Personal income from employment or business activities is subject to two main taxes, the social tax or payroll tax and the personal income tax. The social tax, amounting to 33 percent of personal income, is levied without any exemptions. The personal income tax is at a flat rate levied on taxable income, i.e. personal income minus the basic exemption and a few other deductions including interest payments on housing loans, educational expenses, charitable donations and some pension contributions. Taxable in-

come is subject to a flat tax rate initially set at 26 percent but reduced gradually from 2005.

The main difference between the tax treatment of personal income from employment and personal income from business activities is that the former is subject to third-party reporting, while this is not the case for income from business activities. Revenue and deductible business expenses are reported to the tax authorities by the taxpayer and typically without any third-party reporting. This makes it fairly easy to underreport personal income by leaving out revenue or by overstating business deductions. Overstating of deductions is aided by the fact that in some cases there is no clear distinction between business expenses and personal expenses. It may for instance be possible to report housing costs, office equipment and car purchases as business expenses.

Different studies provide quite a broad range of estimates of the size of the shadow economy in Estonia, an outcome that partly reflects the difficulty of providing estimates of activities that are kept in the shadow. The estimates are generally comparable to those for other EU countries from central and eastern Europe and southern Europe (Schneider and Williams 201; Tafenau, Herwartz and Schneider 2010).

3. Data

The empirical analyses in this paper are based on data from the 2002-2007 versions of the Estonian Household Budget Survey. The end point of the sample is dictated by the fact that the data collection was halted in 2008-2009 and when it resumed in 2010 it started following the guidelines of the European Commission (EC 2003). As a result detailed income data are no longer collected. We therefore restrict the sample to the period 2002-2007, for which the survey contains detailed monthly data on spending and income.

The interview unit is the household, defined as people who live in the same main residence and share their expenses. The household is asked to designate the person in the household with the highest income as the *household head*. The household is then asked to provide information for a given month, and consumption, income and all other data relate to this particular month.

The Estonian HBS contains detailed information on twelve different consumption categories, but we follow P&W and use only the category depicting spending on food, including spending on eating outside the home. Pissarides and Weber (1989) argue that food consumption is the spending category which is most reliably reported by the self-employed.

Households provide detailed listings of different income sources for the month of the interview. The *after-tax* current income of the household is the sum of five different income components, i.e. income from employment, income from self-employment, property and capital income, transfers, and other income components. The income from self-employment, which we label *business income*, includes income from registered self-employment activities, provision of services, domestic production, intermediation and trade, and other business activities.

The Estonian HBS is unique in that the household is asked to specify not only the *current* monthly after-tax income of the household in the month for which data are collected, but also the typical or *regular* monthly after-tax income. The question about regular income is asked after the detailed data on the current income have been provided. The regular income excludes temporary or extraordinary income components. The properties of the regular and transitory income components are investigated in detail in Kukk et al. (2016) and their findings suggest that the regular income variable is a useful measure of the permanent income which Pissarides and Weber (1989) suggest as an explanatory variable.

By using permanent rather than current income it is possible to provide a point estimate of the extent of underreporting instead of a range. If current income is used, it is only possible to provide a range for the extent of underreporting as additional assumptions on the covariation between permanent income and underreporting are needed (Pissarides and Weber 1989). We can use the regular income in the estimations, but as a robustness check we also provide the estimations using the current income measure. Moreover, we include a temporary income measure as a control variable to account for excess sensitivity which may be misinterpreted as income underreporting. Temporary income is computed as the difference between current income and regular income.

The spending on food is deflated by the HICP consumer price index for food, while the income variables are deflated by the overall HICP index; the resulting real variables are expressed in 2005 prices.

The Estonian HBS makes it possible to identify households prone to underreporting in two different ways. Under the first method a household is seen as prone to underreporting if it reports business income above a given threshold. It is noticeable that households with business income typically also have income from other sources; very few households report having only income from self-employment.

The second method of identification can be derived from a question in the Estonia HBS on the employment status of the household head. If the household head has several income sources, it is instructed to report the employment status for the main income source. The household has the status of self-employed if the household head is “an entrepreneur with employees, including farmer”, “a sole proprietor or freelancer” or “employed in a family enterprise, including farmer”.

It is notable that this means of identification refers only to the employment status of the *household head*; in households with two adults the status of the other adult is not known.

The HBS makes it possible to include a large number of control variables in the estimations. The variables include a dummy indicating the region in which the household resides; the age, gender, nationality and education level of the household head; the number of children under 16; and a dummy variable that takes the value one for households with two income earners. Unfortunately no explicit wealth variables are available in the Estonian HBS; instead we include a dummy taking the value one if the household rents its accommodation and a dummy taking the value one if the household owns real estate in which it does not reside. A list of the variables along with summary statistics is provided in Column (A1.1) in Table A.1 in the Appendix.

All previous studies have restricted the sample to households with two adults. We also focus on households with two adults as this facilitates comparisons with the previous studies and ensures that a large number of observations are available. However, we examine the robustness of the results by repeating the estimations using a sample of households with only one adult. Table 1 shows how the two identification schemes divide the sample of approximately 6000 households with two adults into different groups. Less than 10 percent of the households report their status as self-employed. Approximately one third of the households with the status of self-employed do not report any business income, while almost half of the households which report to be wage earners earn some business income. In other words, many households receive both wage income and business income; households with status as self-employed comprise only a small part of the households who report receiving business income.

Table 1. Number of households using different definitions of self-employment

		Reported employment status		
		Wage earners	Self-employed	Total
Share of business income in reported income	0%	2923	162	3085
	> 0%	2565	366	2931
	Total	5488	528	6016

Note: Sample of households with two adults.

Source: Estonian HBS 2002–2007.

Summary statistics for the four groups are provided in Columns (A1.2)-(A1.5) in Table A.1 in the Appendix. The number of households with no reported business income is broadly the same as the number of households with some reported business income. The share of business income in reported income is very small in many of the households who report earning some business income.

The large number of households with some business income suggests that many households combine employment and self-employment. According to Eamets (2008) a substantial share of employed people with more than one job are self-employed in their second job. In order to encourage entrepreneurship, the Estonian authorities made efforts in the beginning of the 2000s to simplify the legislation regulating entrepreneurship, including the registration of a company or a business as a sole proprietor (Leetmaa and Võrk 2007).³

Table A.1 in the Appendix shows the mean of regular income and food consumption for different groups of households with two adults. The groups exhibit very different shares of food consumption out of regular income. This observation motivates a detailed investigation of the consequences of using different identification methods.

4. Empirical model

This section provides a brief description of the P&W methodology used in the paper; more details on the derivation of the model are provided in Pissarides and Weber (1989), while Kukk and Staehr (2014) discuss the modified version that applies when data on regular income are available. The main assumption is that the self-employed, seen as prone to underreporting, and other households only differ in the extent to which the households report their income. Household i reports regular income $Y_i^{\text{rep-reg}}$, where regular income is the income when temporary income components are excluded. The log of total permanent income can be expressed as:

$$\log Y_i = \log Y_i^{\text{rep-reg}} + \log \kappa_i. \quad (1)$$

To obtain the total permanent income Y_i , the reported regular income $Y_i^{\text{rep-reg}}$ has to be multiplied by a factor κ_i ; income underreporting is present if $\kappa_i \geq 1$. Self-employed households are generally assumed to report a smaller fraction of their total regular income than households in the comparison group.⁴ It is assumed that κ_i is a random variable with a log-normal distribution so $\log \kappa_i$ is a random variable with mean μ_κ and variance $\sigma_\kappa^2 > 0$. The average underreporting factor can be found as:

$$\kappa = \exp(\mu_\kappa + \frac{1}{2} \sigma_\kappa^2). \quad (2)$$

The first step is to estimate a food consumption function or Engel curve. As consumption decisions are determined by the total permanent income but only reported regular income is observed, eq. (1) is used to replace the total income in the Engel curve:

$$\log C_i = \alpha + \beta \log Y_i^{\text{rep-reg}} + \beta \log \kappa_i + X_i' \delta + \varepsilon_i. \quad (3)$$

The variable $\log C_i$ is the log real food consumption and the variable $\log Y_i^{\text{rep-reg}}$ is the log

reported regular real income. The control variables in the column vector X_i seek to account for household heterogeneity, which affects food consumption. The error term is labelled ε_i .

When the self-employed households, i.e. households prone to underreporting, and a relevant comparison group are pinned down by the chosen identification method, the following food consumption model can be estimated:

$$\log C_i = \alpha + \beta \log Y_i^{\text{rep-reg}} + \gamma D_i + X_i' \delta + \varepsilon_i. \quad (4)$$

The dummy variable D_i takes the value one for any household identified as self-employed. The coefficient γ equals $\beta \mu_\kappa$. The computation of κ in eq. (2) uses the estimated coefficients γ and β and the variance of the underreporting factor, σ_v^2 , which is not known.

For the computation of σ_v^2 income regressions are estimated for the two subsamples separately:

$$\log Y_i^{\text{rep-reg}} = \alpha + Z_i' \phi + \omega_i, \quad (5)$$

where Z_i is a column vector of variables determining the reported regular income and ω_i is unexplained variation. The variance of the error term of the income regression in eq. (5) is denoted σ_{SE}^2 for the group of self-employed households and σ_0^2 for the comparison group. It is assumed that the source of any difference between the variances of the error terms in the income regressions of the different subgroups stems from the variance in the log underreporting factor.⁵

The mean underreporting factor can then be found as:

$$\kappa = \exp\left(\frac{\gamma}{\beta} + \frac{1}{2}(\sigma_{SE}^2 - \sigma_0^2)\right). \quad (6)$$

The mean underreporting factor κ is the figure by which the regular income reported by the

self-employed households must be multiplied in order for these households to attain on average the same propensity for food consumption as households in the comparison group. A mean underreporting factor of $\kappa > 1$ entails that the self-employed households underreport their income to a larger extent than the comparison group do.

Another way to express the extent of underreporting is the underreporting share s defined as:

$$s = \frac{(\kappa - 1)}{\kappa}. \quad (7)$$

The underreporting share s is the mean share of unreported income in total (reported and unreported) income relative to the comparison group. If the comparison group does not underreport income, the underreporting share in eq. (7) can be seen as the share of total income not reported.

The standard errors of κ and s cannot be computed directly because the standard errors of σ_{SE}^2 and σ_0^2 are not known. The standard errors can, however, be obtained by bootstrapping the sequence of regressions used to estimate κ and s . First, the income regressions are estimated separately for the group prone to underreporting and for the comparison group, from which the standard errors of σ_{SE}^2 and σ_0^2 are recouped. Second, the consumption model is estimated. Finally, the underreporting factor κ and the share of unreported income s are estimated. The full sequence is replicated 400 times, providing the distribution of the estimated κ and s from which the standard deviation of the parameters is calculated.

5. Underreporting results using different identification schemes

We start the empirical analysis by examining the results when each of the identification methods is applied separately. The first method is the straightforward division of the full sample into households where the household head is reported to be self-employed and households where the household head is reported to be a wage earner. The second method is the division of the sample by the reported business income of the household.

The second method gives rise to a minor complication as the share of business income is a continuous variable which is turned into a binary variable by using a cut-off value. There is no ex ante preferable cut-off value. Pissarides and Weber (1989) use a cut-off value of 25 percent, so that households with business income of over 25 percent of their reported income are considered as self-employed and prone to underreporting, and the rest are considered as wage earners, including those who report business income of less than 25 percent of their total income. Shuetze (2002) uses a cut-off point of 30 percent; a cut-off at zero is not used in any studies. Kukk and Staehr (2014) investigate the income underreporting of households with different shares of business income in Estonia and show that households with even a small share of business income underreport income, though the share is relatively small. The study uses a threshold of 20 percent for households with business income and excludes from the comparison group households with a smaller share of business income. As we are comparing the results of two identification methods, we prefer not to exclude any households from the sample when using business income as an indicator and we therefore use a cut-off point of zero when identifying the households prone to underreporting based on their reported business income.

We estimate the consumption model in eq. (4) on monthly data from January 2002 to

December 2007. The coefficients α , β and γ are to be estimated along with those in the vector δ . The control variables in the column vector X_i include the log temporary real income, the demeaned age of the household head and its squared value, the number of children aged below 16, a dummy for two income earners in the household, a dummy for renting of the main residence, and a dummy for ownership of real estate beyond the main residence. Finally, 71 monthly dummies are included as control variables to account for time-dependent aggregate shocks.

We use cross-sectional data and can therefore not control for unobserved heterogeneity so the income variable $\log Y_i^{\text{rep-reg}}$ is likely to be correlated with the error term, which calls for the variable to be instrumented. We estimate several different model specifications and for comparability the same set of instruments have been used in all specifications, i.e. the education level, gender and nationality of the household head and regional dummies for the log regular income $\log Y_i^{\text{rep-reg}}$. According to the standard Mincer model, education level is an important determinant of employment income (Mincer 1974). Empirical studies for Estonia have shown significant income gaps between men and women and between people of different ethnicities (Leping and Toomet 2008). Regional NUTS-3 dummies are used to capture the regional labour market situation (Blanchflower and Oswald 1995, Verkulevičiūtė-Kriukienė 2015).⁶

The results of the estimation of the consumption model in eq. (4) are shown in Table A.2 in the Appendix for the two identification methods considered. The estimated coefficients are very similar across the two cases; only the coefficient of the dummy indicating underreporting households varies substantially, suggesting different underreporting factors.

Table 2 shows the average underreporting factor κ defined in eq. (6) and the underreporting

share s defined in eq. (7), both relative to the comparison group. The results are different when different methods are used to identify the households prone to underreporting. Note that the way in which the group of households prone to underreporting is identified also determines the group taken to be the comparison group. Column (2.1) shows the results when the identification is based on reported employment status. The reported income of households reporting their status as self-employed must be multiplied by the underreporting factor $\kappa = 1.386$ for these households to have the same propensity for food consumption as households with the status of wage earners. It follows that the households with self-employment status leave approximately 28 percent of their total income unreported. These measures of underreporting are, as whenever the P&W approach is used, relative to the underreporting in the reference group, in this case the households with the status of wage earners.

Table 2. Estimates of income underreporting relative to the comparison group using different identification methods

	(2.1)	(2.2)
	Reported employment status ^a	Reported share of business income ^b
Underreporting factor κ	1.386 (0.068)	1.747 (0.057)
Underreporting share s	0.279 (0.036)	0.428 (0.018)
No. of obs.	6016	6016

^a The underreporting group consists of household in which the head is reported to be self-employed, while the comparison group consists of households where the head is reported to be a wage earner.

^b The underreporting group consists of households that report some business income, while the comparison group consists of households which do not report any business income.

Note: Sample of households with two adults. Calculations using the consumption estimations in Columns (A2.1) and (A2.2) in Table A.2 in the Appendix. Bootstrapped standard errors are reported in parentheses.

Column (2.2) shows the underreporting results when the households prone to underreporting are taken to be those that report business income above 0. The underreporting

factor $\kappa = 1.747$ is substantially larger than before; the reported income of households with any business income must be multiplied by 1.7 to attain the same consumption propensity as for households with no business income. This implies that the households with business income above 0 leave around 43 percent of their total income unreported compared to households with no business income.⁷

A higher underreporting factor for households with a higher share of business income is an expected outcome if the underreporting pertains mainly to business income. The estimated underreporting factor shows how much income is unreported from total (reported and unreported) income, and it is reasonable to assume that the underreporting factor should be higher for households with a larger share of business income. Table S.1 in the online supplementary materials provides the estimates of the underreporting factor for households with different shares of business income, confirming that a higher share of business income concurs with a higher share of unreported income.⁸ When households with some business income are excluded from the comparison group of wage earners, the underreporting factor is 2.6 and the underreporting share is 62 percent.

This paper focuses on the consequences of the use of different identification methods. Kukk and Staehr (2014) discuss possible reasons for such extensive underreporting in Estonia and point in particular to the possibility of private spending being reported as deductible business expenses. Paulus (2015b) similarly finds very substantial underreporting using Estonian data and provides some explanation for the results.

The results in Table 2 taken in combination paint an interesting picture. The two identification methods lead to markedly different results. The share of unreported income is

estimated to be substantially larger when the households prone to underreporting are identified using the share of business income than when they are identified using their employment status. The differences are even more striking when the standard approach of the other studies is applied and a cut-off point at some positive value is used for business income.

As a robustness test, we have run the estimations using current income rather than regular income; in this case we can only provide the range of the estimated underreporting factor. The estimated coefficients of the consumption model and the estimated underreporting factors are given in Table S.2 in the online supplementary materials. The coefficients of the consumption model are very similar to those of the baseline model which are given in Table A.2. The range of the estimated underreporting factor is quite large, as in other studies, but the differences between the results using the different identification methods are evident.

These findings show the importance of the choice of identification method. The results of studies using the P&W methodology must be interpreted in light of their chosen identification method. Using only the reported employment status we attain the results shown in Column (2.1), where underreporting is estimated at around 28 percent of total income relative to the comparison group. This result is in the same range as the results for the USA, Finland and Sweden which identify the self-employed by their reported employment status, cf. Engström and Holmlund (2009), Hurst, Li and Pugsley (2014), and Johansson (2005). Our results based on Estonian data suggest, however, that the share of underreporting is substantially higher when the households prone to underreporting are identified from their reported business income.

6. Underreporting results combining different identification schemes

To obtain a better understanding of the factors behind the results of the different identification methods in Section 5, we distinguish between the different groups or sub-samples shown in Table 1. This entails combining information on the employment status and the share of business income of the households. The objective is to examine whether combining the two different criteria leads to a better identification of the households that are prone to underreporting.

6.1 The baseline estimations

We take as the comparison group the households of wage earners in which the household head is reported to be a wage earner *and* which do not report any business income. We consider three groups of households prone to underreporting, indexed by g and differentiated by the way the underreporting households are identified. The first group ($g = 1$) contains households in which the household head is a wage earner *and* the household reports some business income. The second group ($g = 2$) contains households in which the head is reported to be self-employed *and* the household reports some business income. The third group ($g = 3$) consist of households where the head is self-employed *and* no business income is reported. The number of households is 2565 in the first group, 366 in the second group and 162 in the third group, as also reported in Table 1.

The more homogeneous groups defined above can easily be mapped onto the groups used in the estimations presented in Table 2. In Column (2.1) the second and third groups are in the group prone to underreporting, whereas the first group is included in the comparison group together with the group of wage earners without business income. In Column (2.2) however, the first and the second groups comprise the underreporting group while the third group and the wage

earners are in the comparison group.

Using the more fine-grained division of the sample leads to the following consumption model:

$$\log C_i = \alpha + \beta \log Y_i^{\text{rep-reg}} + \gamma_1 D_{1i} + \gamma_2 D_{2i} + \gamma_3 D_{3i} + X_i' \delta + \varepsilon_i, \quad (8)$$

where the self-employment dummies D_1 , D_2 and D_3 are used for the three groups of underreporting households identified using different identification methods. The estimated coefficients γ_1 , γ_2 and γ_3 of the dummies are used to compute the underreporting factors $\kappa_g = \kappa_1$, κ_2 and κ_3 and the underreporting shares $s_g = s_1$, s_2 and s_3 for the three groups of households.

The estimation results for the consumption model are reported in Column (A2.3) in Table A.2 in the Appendix. Column (3.1) in Table 3 shows the computed underreporting factor κ_g for each group and Column (3.2) shows the corresponding underreporting shares s_g , both being relative to the comparison group of wage earners without any business income.

The estimations where the underreporting households are identified through their business income provide higher underreporting results when the household head has the status of self-employed than when the head is a wage earner. The income of wage earners with business income should be multiplied by 1.7 to attain a total income comparable to that of the comparison group of wage earners who do not report any business income. The income of households in which the household head has the status of self-employed and which have some business income should be multiplied by 2.2. In other words, the underreporting share for households stating themselves to be wage earners is 41 percent and the share for households stated as self-employed is 55 percent, in both cases relative to the comparison group of wage earners without any business income.

Table 3. Estimates of income underreporting combining different identification schemes. Households with two adults.

	(3.1)	(3.2)	(3.3)	(3.4)
	Full sample		Matched sample	
	Underreporting factor κ_g	Underreporting share s_g	Underreporting factor κ_g	Share of income unreported relative to the income of the comparison group
Wage earners, share of business income > 0	1.705 (0.056)	0.413 (0.019)	2.295 (0.150)	0.564 (0.030)
Self-employed, share of business income > 0	2.214 (0.137)	0.548 (0.029)	2.148 (0.124)	0.534 (0.028)
Self-employed, share of business income = 0	1.054 (0.071)	0.051 (0.072)	1.026 (0.065)	0.025 (0.070)
Wald-test ($H_0: \kappa_1 = \kappa_2$)	19.19 [0.000]	..	0.82 [0.364]	..
Wald-test ($H_0: \kappa_3 = 1$)	0.58 [0.448]	..	0.16 [0.693]	..
No. of obs.	6016		3817	

Note: Calculations using the consumption estimations in Column (A2.4) in Table A.2. The comparison group of the estimations contains households who report that the household head is a wage earner and the household does not earn any business income. In the matched sample the group of wage earners with business income above 0 is matched to the group of the self-employed with business income above 0 based on the share of business income. Bootstrapped standard errors are reported in parentheses below the parameter estimates. A Wald-test provides the χ^2 statistic for the null hypothesis while the p -value is given in square brackets below.

6.2. Estimations with matched samples

Further analysis suggests that the difference between wage earners and the self-employed with business income largely stems from the different distributions of the share of business income in reported income among wage earners and the self-employed. The left panel in Figure 1 shows the distribution of the share of business income for the two groups and it is clear that there are a substantial number of wage earners with a relatively low share of business income. To take account of the different shares of business income across the two groups, a one-to-one matching was carried out using the share of business income. For each household in the group of the self-

employed, a household with a similar share of business income was chosen from the group of wage earners.⁹ As a result a total of 366 households (rather than 2565 households) were included in the group of wage earners with business income; the same number of households is in the group of self-employed with business income. The right panel in Figure 1 confirms that the distribution of the share of business income after the matching is comparable in the two samples.

Figure 1. Kernel density estimates

Note: The full sample includes all wage earners with business income. In the matched sample households of wage earners with business income are matched to households of the self-employed using the share of business income.

The underreporting results using the matched sample are given in Columns (3.3) and (3.4) in Table 3. The underreporting factor is 2.3 for households where the head is a wage earner and this is not statistically different from the estimated underreporting factor for households where

the head is self-employed. In other words, the difference in the results between wage earners and the self-employed is marginal when the share of business income is taken into account. It can be seen from Columns (A1.3) and (A1.4) in Table A.1 in the Appendix that these households exhibit quite comparable socio-demographic variables, suggesting that the two groups are relatively similar. As seen in Columns (A1.2) and (A1.3), the profile of wage earners without business income is somewhat different from the profile of wage earners with business income, implying that the two groups should not be pooled.

The sample has hitherto comprised only households with two adults who are active in the labour market. Such a sample composition is chosen in all studies using the P&W method, as the homogeneous sample makes it more likely that any differences in food consumption are driven by underreporting. Our results utilising the reported employment status may, however, be questioned as we observe the employment status only for the household head and no information on the employment status of the second adult is available. To ensure that this particularity does not drive the results, we repeat the estimations in eq. (8) for households with only one adult so that the employment status is known for all the adults in the household. The results for households with one adult are provided in Table S.3 in the online supplementary materials, and they show that the results are comparable to those for households with two adults.

6.3 Discussion of the results

It follows from Column (2.1) that if the identification is based entirely on reported employment status, the estimated share of underreporting relative to the comparison group is around 28 percent of total income. However, we obtain quite different results when we split those

with self-employment status into two groups. Column (3.2) shows that the share of underreporting by households whose status is self-employed varies markedly depending on the reported business income; the underreporting is estimated to be around 55 percent if business income is reported, but essentially zero if no business income is reported.

The results in Table 3 explain those in Table 2. The estimated underreporting share of 28 percent when there is no conditioning on reported business income, shown in Column (2.1) in Table 2, derives from a mixture of different effects. First, it follows from Table 1 that 47 percent of the comparison group of wage earners in Column (2.1) in Table 2 earn some business income, while Table 3 shows that wage earners with business income underreport 41 percent of their total income. If it is assumed that wage earners without business income report their income truthfully, the average underreporting in the comparison group would be $0.47 \cdot 0.41 \approx 19$ percent. Second, as the group of self-employed in Column (2.1) in Table 2 includes the self-employed without business income, the estimations essentially give the weighted average of the estimated underreporting share for the two sub-samples, i.e. the self-employed with and without business income, which is $0.69 \cdot 0.55 + 0.31 \cdot 0.05 \approx 40$ percent. Column (2.1) shows the *additional* underreporting of the self-employed relative to the underreporting of wage earners which is $(0.4 - 0.19)/(1 - 0.19) \approx 25$ percent, which is very close to the estimated underreporting share of 28 percent in Column (2.1) in Table 2.¹⁰

When the wage earners without business income are used as a comparison group and other groups are taken to be prone to underreporting, the estimations exhibit the underreporting of different groups relative to the *same* comparison group. The estimations in Table 3 reveal that the estimated underreporting shares s_1 and s_2 are similar while s_3 is very small. In other words, the

reported employment status of the household does not matter if the share of reported business income is taken into account. Conditional on the reported share of business income, households with the status of self-employed and households of wage earners appear to underreport income to the same extent.

The results in Table 3 are robust and also emerge when we use OLS estimations instead of IV estimations, or when non-durable consumption is used instead of food consumption; see Tables S.4 and S.5 in the online supplementary materials. Finally, additional robustness tests have been carried out using smaller sets of instruments (not reported), but the estimation results are very similar, indicating that the results are not sensitive to the choice of instruments.

The underreporting factor for households with the status of self-employed but no reported business income is not statistically different from 1; there is no sign of income underreporting for this group relative to the comparison group of wage earners without business income. It follows from Table 1 that approximately one third of the households who have the status of self-employed do not report any business income. A possible reason for the absence of business income in households that report their status as self-employed could be that they are fully concealing the self-employment income, but this hypothesis is ruled out by the finding of no underreporting. It is therefore likely that these households indeed have no income because of temporary inactivity or adverse conditions affecting their business.

7. Final comments

Limited third-party reporting implies that the self-employed have ample opportunities to underreport their income. The methodology of Pissarides and Weber (1989) is an ingenious means of assessing the extent of possible income underreporting by this group. The studies applying the P&W methodology use two different ways to identify the households prone to underreporting, i.e. the reported employment status and the share of reported business income in reported income. This paper is the first to examine in detail the effect of the choice of method for identifying underreporting households when the P&W methodology is used. The estimations are implemented using survey data and although no firm conclusion can be drawn about the reporting to the tax authorities, the results may be seen as an indication of possible underreporting to the tax authorities (Hurst, Li and Pugsley 2014; Pissarides and Weber 1989).

The Estonian Household Budget Survey contains detailed information on both consumption and income measures along with the reported employment status, and this makes it possible to use either of the two main identification schemes. The share of unreported income is estimated to be around 28 percent of total (reported and unreported) income if the employment status is used for identifying households prone to underreporting, while it is 43 percent if households prone to underreporting are identified using reported business income. The unconditional estimates are based on sample splits along only one dimension as is customarily done in the literature using the P&W method.

Additional insights emerge when the sample is split along both dimensions, i.e. business income and reported employment status. When the distributions of the business income shares for wage earners and self-employed are matched, the extent of underreporting turns out to be very

similar for the reported self-employed with business income and for reported wage earners with business income. These results are robust to different household compositions, including households with one adult. The upshot is that the identification method is of material importance, as reporting of business income appears to be a good indicator of potential underreporting; a substantial share of households prone to income underreporting are overlooked if only households which report themselves to be self-employed are considered prone to underreporting.

Appendix

Table A.1. Descriptive sample statistics

	(A1.1)	(A1.2)	(A1.3)	(A1.4)	(A1.5)
	Full sample	Reported wage earners, business income = 0	Reported wage earners, business income > 0	Reported self-employed, business income > 0	Reported self-employed, business income = 0
Sample size	6016	2923	2565	366	162
Log (Food consumption)	7.72	7.55	7.88	7.98	7.68
Log (Current income)	9.07	9.06	9.08	9.01	9.20
Log (Regular income)	8.96	8.98	8.92	8.93	9.20
Share of business income	0.08	0.00	0.13	0.40	0.00
Age	43.47	42.11	44.77	46.21	41.12
Female	0.38	0.40	0.40	0.20	0.14
Non-Estonian	0.25	0.38	0.13	0.09	0.30
Education level 1	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.01
Education level 2	0.52	0.51	0.53	0.46	0.46
Education level 3	0.43	0.44	0.42	0.48	0.53
Number of children	0.74	0.66	0.80	0.87	0.92
Region North	0.29	0.41	0.16	0.15	0.45
Region Northeast	0.11	0.16	0.06	0.02	0.04
Region Central	0.13	0.10	0.17	0.17	0.07
Region West	0.17	0.12	0.20	0.27	0.19
Region South	0.31	0.21	0.41	0.39	0.25
Two income earners	0.55	0.56	0.53	0.57	0.54
Owning second property	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.07	0.10
Renting main residence	0.07	0.09	0.06	0.03	0.10

Notes: Table gives the mean values of the variables; socio-demographic variables are for the household head while the economic variables are for the household.

Table A.2. Full estimations of IV regression model. Dependent variable: food consumption

	(A2.1)	(A2.2)	(A2.3)	(A2.4)
	Reported employment status ^a	Reported share of business income ^b	Two adults Full sample	Two adults Matched sample
Log regular income (β)	0.567*** (0.032)	0.596*** (0.031)	0.588*** (0.031)	0.613*** (0.039)
Self-employment dummy (γ)	0.152 (0.024)
Business income dummy (γ)	..	0.320*** (0.012)
Dummy for wage earners, business income > 0	0.303*** (0.012)	0.456*** (0.032)
Dummy for the self-employed, business income > 0	0.429*** (0.028)	0.429*** (0.028)
Dummy for the self-employed, business income = 0	-0.005 (0.041)	-0.022* (0.041)
Log temporary income	0.213*** (0.018)	0.183*** (0.016)	0.184*** (0.016)	0.157*** (0.017)
Age – mean age	0.004*** (0.001)	0.002*** (0.001)	0.002*** (0.001)	0.002*** (0.001)
(Age – mean age) ² /10	-0.002*** (0.000)	-0.002*** (0.000)	-0.002*** (0.000)	-0.002*** (0.000)
Number of children	0.110*** (0.008)	0.087*** (0.008)	0.086*** (0.008)	0.092*** (0.010)
Two income earners	-0.053*** (0.018)	-0.059*** (0.017)	-0.058*** (0.017)	-0.057*** (0.022)
Owning second real estate	-0.074*** (0.020)	-0.062*** (0.019)	-0.059*** (0.019)	-0.069*** (0.025)
Renting main residence	-0.045* (0.025)	-0.030 (0.024)	-0.028 (0.024)	0.045 (0.028)
Constant	2.729*** (0.273)	2.322*** (0.263)	2.396*** (0.262)	2.230*** (0.333)
R^2	0.228	0.296	0.302	0.287
R^2 of the first regression	0.424	0.425	0.428	0.435
F -stat of the first regression [p-value]	54.53 [0.000]	54.53 [0.000]	54.84 [0.000]	26.81 [0.000]
No. of obs.	6016	6016	6016	3817

^a Self-employed vs. wage earners.

^b Business income > 0 vs. business income = 0.

Notes: IV estimations. 71 monthly dummies are included in the estimations but are not shown in the table. In the matched sample the group of wage earners with business income above 0 is matched to the group of self-employed with business income above 0 using the share of business income. Robust standard errors are reported in round parentheses below the coefficient estimates.

Superscripts ***, ** and * indicate that the coefficient is statistically different from 0 at the 1%, 5% and 10% levels respectively.

F -stat is the test statistic for the Wald test of overall goodness of the fit of the first regression.

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Endnotes

¹ The Living Cost and Food Survey in the UK collects data on weekly spending with diaries while requiring the households to report only their usual weekly income without detailing the source. The Panel Survey of Income Dynamics (PSID) contains detailed income data but the survey collects food consumption data at a rather general level as no diary is used.

² An example of this is the US Consumer Expenditure Survey (CEX), in which households report annual income for the previous year, while consumption data are collected for the current quarter.

³ The application can be submitted to the registrar electronically without notary involvement and at low cost, and the registration is typically granted only a few hours after it is submitted. In addition, it is relatively simple to file tax returns through the website of the tax authorities.

⁴ The assumption of no income underreporting has customarily been used for the comparison group. However, the current specification makes it possible to interpret the results in terms of income underreporting *in addition to* the underreporting by the comparison group. This interpretation is useful if wage earners exhibit substantial income underreporting. Studies suggest, however, that underreporting of wage income may be relatively modest in Estonia (Kriz et al. 2008, Williams 2009).

⁵ After controlling for household specific economic and socio-demographic characteristics, the variance of the residual in the regression of regular income in eq. (5) contains unexplained variation in regular income and deviations of total from reported regular income. When the unexplained variation in regular income has the same variance for the underreporting group and the comparison group, mainly stemming from omitted variables, then the difference between the re-

sidual income variance of the two groups derives from the variance σ_v^2 . This assumption is used by Pissarides and Weber (1989) as well as by other authors applying the method.

⁶ In the dataset the education level, gender and nationality are valid instruments in all specifications while there is some doubt about the regional dummies in some specifications. There is no apparent reason for regional dummies to affect food consumption in Estonia as prices are very similar across the country due to the small size of the market and relatively short distances between the regions. There are however substantial regional disparities in income and employment opportunities in Estonia which cannot be accounted for by variables for education, gender and ethnicity (Verkulevičiūtė-Kriukienė 2015). We obtain qualitatively similar results when using a smaller number of instruments (not shown; the estimations are available upon request).

⁷ A cut-off point at some positive value for business income is typically used in studies exploiting the P&W methodology. For comparison we carried out estimations with a cut-off point of 20 percent where the comparison group consists of households with no business income or with business income of up to 20 percent of their reported income. The underreporting factor is 2.3 and the underreporting share is around 56 percent for the households with business income above 20 percent (not shown).

⁸ Kukk and Staehr (2014) discuss in detail the importance of the threshold value of the share of business income in estimating underreporting of income. The present paper does not consider different thresholds for the share of business income as the main focus is on the comparison of different identification schemes. As the employment status can take only binary values, the business income measure is similarly kept as a binary variable.

⁹ For selection of the matching pairs we use *single nearest neighbour matching* with a common support and without replacement.

¹⁰ This can also be expressed in algebra. If in the comparison group a fraction λ_0 are pure wage earners with 0 underreporting and a fraction $\lambda_1 = 1 - \lambda_0$ underreport income by the share of s_1 , the average share of underreported income in the comparison group is $\lambda_1 s_1$. The underreporting group consists of a fraction λ_2 that underreports s_2 and a fraction $\lambda_3 = 1 - \lambda_2$ whose underreporting share is s_3 , implying that on average $\lambda_2 s_2 + (1 - \lambda_2) s_3$ of the income is not reported in this group. The estimated underreported share in Column (2.1) can be calculated as $(\lambda_2 s_2 + (1 - \lambda_2) s_3 - \lambda_1 s_1) / (1 - \lambda_1 s_1)$.

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Supplementary materials

Identification of Households Prone to Income Underreporting: Employment Status or Reported Business Income?

Public Finance Review

Merike Kukk and Karsten Staehr

Table S.1. Estimates of income underreporting for households with different shares of business income.
Dependent variable: food consumption

	(A3.1)	(A3.2)	(A3.3)
	Estimated coefficients	Underreporting factor κ_g	Underreporting share s_g
Log regular income	0.625*** (0.031)
Dummy for business income < 5%	0.131*** (0.016)	1.233 (0.036)	0.189 (0.024)
Dummy for business income 5–10%	0.290*** (0.017)	1.561 (0.055)	0.359 (0.026)
Dummy for business income 10–20%	0.444*** (0.019)	2.005 (0.081)	0.501 (0.020)
Dummy for business income 20–50%	0.581*** (0.039)	2.380 (0.131)	0.580 (0.024)
Dummy for business income \geq 50%	0.546*** (0.028)	2.988 (0.230)	0.665 (0.030)
R^2	0.331		
No. of obs.	6016		

Notes: Column (A3.1) shows IV estimations with GMM estimator. Education level, nationality, gender and five regional dummies are used as instruments. Log temporary income, age and age squared of the household head, the number of children, two income earners, ownership of a second real estate property, renting the main residence, and 71 monthly time fixed effects are included in the estimations, but the results are not shown in the table. Robust standard errors are reported in round parentheses below the coefficient estimates. Superscripts ***, ** and * indicate that the coefficient is statistically different from 0 at the 1%, 5% and 10% levels respectively. Columns (A3.2) and (A3.3) show underreporting results using the consumption estimations in Column (A3.1). Bootstrapped standard errors are reported in parentheses below the parameter estimates.

Table S.2. Estimates of income underreporting from different identification methods using current income variable. Dependent variable: food consumption

	(A4.1)	(A4.2)
	Reported employment status ^a	Reported share of business income ^b
<i>A. Consumption model</i>		
Log current income (β)	0.545*** (0.032)	0.553*** (0.031)
Self-employment dummy (γ)	0.165*** (0.027)	...
Business income dummy (γ)	...	0.287*** (0.013)
Age – mean age	0.004*** (0.001)	0.002*** (0.001)
(Age – mean age) ² /10	-0.002*** (0.000)	-0.002*** (0.000)
Number of children	0.103*** (0.009)	0.083*** (0.008)
Two income earners	-0.043** (0.018)	-0.039** (0.018)
Owning second real estate	-0.066*** (0.022)	-0.052** (0.021)
Renting main residence	-0.053** (0.027)	-0.040 (0.026)
Constant	2.882*** (0.273)	2.659*** (0.266)
R^2	0.124	0.178
R^2 of the first regression	0.252	0.251
F -stat of the first regression	31.84	31.70
[p-value]	[0.000]	[0.000]

		(A4.1)	(A4.2)
		Reported employment status ^a	Reported share of business income ^b
<i>B. Underreporting</i>			
Underreporting factor κ	Lower bound	1.123 (0.071)	1.488 (0.062)
	Upper bound	1.631 (0.122)	1.901 (0.091)
Underreporting share s	Lower bound	0.109 (0.050)	0.328 (0.027)
	Upper bound	0.387 (0.050)	0.474 (0.025)
No. of obs.		6016	6016

^a Self-employed vs. wage earners. ^b Business income > 0 vs. business income = 0.

Note: Sample of households with two adults. Panel A: IV estimations with GMM estimator. 71 monthly dummies are included in the estimations but are not shown in the table. In the matched sample the group of wage earners with business income above 0 is matched to the group of self-employed with business income above 0 based on the share of business income. Robust standard errors are reported in round parentheses below the coefficient estimates. Superscripts ***, ** and * indicate that the coefficient is statistically different from 0 at the 1%, 5% and 10% levels respectively. Panel B. Calculations using the consumption estimations in Part A. Bootstrapped standard errors are reported in parentheses below the parameter estimates.

Table S.3. Estimates of income underreporting relative to wage earners without any business income. Households with one adult

	(S1.1)	(S1.2)	(S1.3)	(S1.4)
	Full sample		Matched sample	
	Underreporting factor κ_g	Underreporting share s_g	Underreporting factor κ_g	Underreporting share s_g
Wage earners, share of business income > 0	1.939 (0.168)	0.484 (0.042)	2.686 (0.425)	0.628 (0.061)
Self-employed, share of business income > 0	1.983 (0.289)	0.496 (0.103)	1.974 (0.298)	0.493 (0.106)
Self-employed, share of business income = 0	1.271 (0.258)	0.213 (0.149)	1.253 (0.251)	0.202 (0.151)
Wald-test ($H_0: \kappa_1 = \kappa_2$)	0.03 [0.871]	..	2.82 [0.093]	..
Wald-test ($H_0: \kappa_3 = 1$)	1.10 [0.294]	..	1.01 [0.314]	..
No. of obs.	2173		1626	

Note: The comparison group of the estimations contains households who report that the household head is a wage earner and the household does not earn any business income. In the matched sample the group of wage earners with business income above 0 is matched to the group of self-employed with business income above 0 based on the share of business income. Bootstrapped standard errors are reported in parentheses below the parameter estimates. A Wald-test provides the χ^2 statistic for the null hypothesis while the p -value is given in square brackets below.

Table S.4. OLS estimates of income underreporting relative to the comparison group. Households with two adults. Dependent variable: food consumption

	(S2.1)	(S2.2)	(S2.3)	(S2.4)
	Full sample		Matched sample	
	Underreporting factor κ_g	Underreporting factor s_g	Underreporting factor κ_g	Underreporting factor s_g
Wage earners, share of business income > 0	2.258 (0.116)	0.557 (0.022)	3.286 (0.371)	0.695 (0.035)
Self-employed, share of business income > 0	3.182 (0.281)	0.686 (0.029)	3.090 (0.268)	0.676 (0.029)
Self-employed, share of business income = 0	1.183 (0.119)	0.155 (0.095)	1.149 (0.113)	0.130 (0.097)
Wald-test ($H_0: \kappa_1 = \kappa_2$)	14.76 [0.000]	..	0.33 [0.563]	..
Wald-test ($H_0: \kappa_3 = 1$)	2.38 [0.123]	..	1.76 [0.185]	..
No. of obs.	6016		3817	

Note: The comparison group of the estimations contains households who report that the household head is a wage earner and the household does not earn any business income. In the matched sample the group of wage earners with business income above 0 is matched to the group of self-employed with business income above 0 based on the share of business income. Bootstrapped standard errors are reported in parentheses below the parameter estimates. A Wald-test provides the χ^2 statistic for the null hypothesis while the p -value is given in square brackets below.

Table S.5. IV estimates of income underreporting relative to the comparison group. Households with two adults. Dependent variable: non-durable consumption

	(S3.1)	(S3.2)	(S3.3)	(S3.4)
	Full sample		Matched sample	
	Underreporting factor κ_g	Underreporting factor s_g	Underreporting factor κ_g	Underreporting factor s_g
Wage earners, share of business income > 0	1.278 (0.024)	0.218 (0.015)	1.662 (0.081)	0.398 (0.031)
Self-employed, share of business income > 0	1.518 (0.056)	0.341 (0.026)	1.506 (0.051)	0.336 (0.024)
Self-employed, share of business income = 0	1.114 (0.058)	0.103 (0.053)	1.100 (0.052)	0.091 (0.048)
Wald-test ($H_0: \kappa_1 = \kappa_2$)	21.38 [0.000]	..	2.76 [0.096]	..
Wald-test ($H_0: \kappa_3 = 1$)	3.92 [0.049]	..	3.71 [0.054]	..
No. of obs.	6016		3817	

Note: The comparison group of the estimations contains households who report that the household head is a wage earner and the household does not earn any business income. In the matched sample the group of wage earners with business income above 0 is matched to the group of self-employed with business income above 0 based on the share of business income. Bootstrapped standard errors are reported in parentheses below the parameter estimates. A Wald-test provides the χ^2 statistic for the null hypothesis while the p -value is given in square brackets below.